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Abstract: Issues such as dictionary types, vocabulary (the word being interpreted or translated from the dictionary), and the structure of dictionary articles are the main issues in lexicographic theory. Dictionaries are mainly divided into two types: encyclopedic and philological. Concepts related to all fields of science, technology and culture are explained in the encyclopedias. They provide information about natural phenomena, events in social life, and famous people.

Key words: vocabulary, phrases, encyclopedic vocabulary, science, technology.

Dictionaries are of great importance in the theoretical study of the use of words and phrases and in practical teaching of the language. Compilation of different types of dictionaries is of general cultural importance. The dictionary is organized in alphabetical order, and as a convenient guide, it provides knowledge to the public, performs a cultural and educational function. That is why this issue is given great importance. The establishment of special publishing houses and lexicographic institutions can be explained by this.

Issues such as types of vocabulary, composition of vocabulary (the word being explained or translated from the dictionary), and the structure of dictionary articles are the main issues in the lexicographic theory. Dictionaries are mainly divided into two types: encyclopedic and philological. Concepts related to all fields of science, technology and culture are explained in the encyclopedias. They provide information about natural phenomena, events in social life, and famous people. About the word itself, it is limited to showing its origin. Therefore, such dictionaries are called conceptual dictionaries. Usually, such dictionaries also include pictures, maps, and diagrams. In encyclopedias, words and phrases are placed in alphabetical order as the title of the article. Encyclopedic dictionaries are of two types according to their purpose and function: general encyclopedic (encyclopedic) dictionary and field (encyclopedic) dictionary. Examples of common encyclopedias include "British Dictionary" and "Uzbekistan Dictionary". "Encyclopedia of literature" to encyclopedias of a certain field. "Pedagogical Dictionary". "Technical Dictionary". "Agricultural encyclopedia" is included. An encyclopedic dictionary is also called "Qamos" in the East, and "Thesaurus" in the West.

In philological dictionaries, the main attention is paid to the word or phrase and they are explained in every way. Such dictionaries are also arranged in alphabetical order, and the word or phrase to be explained is given as a title.

There are two types of philological dictionaries: general and special philological dictionaries. General philological dictionaries provide an explanation of words used by everyone. They are monolingual, bilingual, multilingual.

Philological dictionaries of one language are divided into several types according to the purpose. For example, explanatory dictionaries, special linguistic dictionaries: etymological dictionary, morpheme dictionary, phraseological dictionary, dictionary of synonyms, orthoepic dictionary, chappa dictionary, dictionary of popular nouns and idioms, dictionary of place names, dictionary of works of famous writers. For example, all the lexical meanings of words are broadly

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explained in an explanatory dictionary. Each word is explained in the form of a small article, and the explained word is shown as a title. Examples of this are "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", 5 volumes, "Oxford Annotated Dictionary of the English Language", 17 volumes "Slovar' sovremennogo russkogo literaturnogo yazg'ka", one volume "Slovar' russkogo yazika" by S.I. Ojegov. will be The "Annotated Dictionary of Russian-International Words" by Olim Usmanov and Renat Doniyorov is included among these. In the dictionary of synonymous words, the shades of meaning and stylistic functions of each word included in the synonymous line are described. An example of this is A. Hojiev's "Annotated dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language". Etymological dictionaries explain the origin of words, their initial form and meaning, and the changes that occurred in them during the development of the language.

M.Fasmer's "Etymological slovar' russkogo yazgka", e.V. Sevortyan's "Etymological slovar' tyurkskih yazgkov", SH. Rahmatullaev's "Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language" is such a dictionary.

A morphemic dictionary is a dictionary that explains the morphemes of words in alphabetical order. In particular, the word to be rewarded is formed from the morphemes of reward (Ian) moq. (See: A.Gulomov, A.N. Tikhonov, R.Kongurov. Uzbek language morpheme dictionary. Tashkent, "Teacher", 1977). In the phraseological dictionary, the semantic and grammatical features of phraseological units (phrases) in the language are explained with the help of examples. It is very useful to juxtapose phraseological homonyms, synonyms and antonyms to give different variants of the same phraseological phrase. Example: Hard-hearted. There is no mercy. Option: stone; stone volunteer; hard-heartedness. Synonym: stone heart-heart stone. Antonym: mind (i) empty; soft heart - soft heart. Analogy: Bagritosh; Mehritosh... [Rakhmatullaev SH. An explanatory phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language. Tashkent. "Teacher", 1978, p. 21].

A dictionary arranged in alphabetical order, depending on the letter of the words, is called a chappa dictionary. For example, words ending with the letter a are given as follows: arfa, bola, dona, sona, pona, tonka, shona. Such a dictionary can be a source for various researches on word formation, morphology and lexicology.

In addition, chappa dictionaries help in learning the phonetic laws of the language, the secrets of poetry (by rhyme). (Book "Obratng'y slovar' uzbekskogo yazgka" by R. Kongurov and A. Tikhonov). There are two types of annotated dictionaries according to their structure: alphabetical dictionaries and nested dictionaries. In dictionaries of the first type, words are given and explained in alphabetical order. The above annotated dictionaries are arranged in this order.

In the second type of dictionaries, only the roots are placed in alphabetical order. And artificial words are explained inside the root article (nest). Such dictionaries provide information about the meaning and form of the words given in the same nest. In the translation dictionaries within two languages, a word or phrase from one language is translated into another language. This includes Russian-Uzbek, English-Uzbek, French-Uzbek, German-Uzbek dictionaries. There are also short translation dictionaries designed for foreign language learners. Sometimes translation dictionaries cover several languages. For example, like "Slovar' naibolee sobukitel'ng'x slov angliyskogo, nemetskogo, franzuskogo i russkogo yazikov".

Philological dictionaries also include dictionaries of various fields. In these, words and terms related to a certain field of science, technology, and production are explained. Terminological dictionaries are the most common among field dictionaries. Such dictionaries are

monolingual, bilingual, multilingual. Monolingual terminological dictionaries explain the terms of one language related to a certain field. These include the books "Slovar' lingvisticheskikh terminov" (1966) by O.S. Akhmanova and "Spravochnik lingvisticheskikh terminov" (1972) by D.E. Rosenthal and M.A. Telenkova, "Dictionary of Geographical Terms" (1964) by H. Hasanov. "Dictionary of Literary Terms" (1967) by H. Hamidiy, SH. Abdullaeva, S. Ibrahimova, "Dictionary of Social and Political Terms" (1976) published under the editorship of Olim Usman can be included. Bilingual terminological dictionaries include N.T. Hotamov's "Brief Russian-Uzbek Terminological Dictionary from Literary Studies" (1969). Sh. Baiburov and N. Takanaev's "Brief Russian-Uzbek terminological dictionary from pedagogy" (1963). An example of multilingual terminological dictionaries is the "Latin-Uzbek-Russian dictionary of normal anatomy" (1964) by A. AAskarov and H. Zohidov.

Dictionary of foreign words is similar to terminological dictionaries. Here, too, words borrowed from foreign languages are explained.

The type of dictionaries is not limited to the above. Thematic, differential, new words, abbreviations, frequency, rhyming dictionaries are also available. For example, in thematic dictionaries, words are grouped according to their meanings. Such dictionaries provide an opportunity to find the most convenient words to express an idea. An example of this is the Roje (Roget) dictionary based on the English language, the last XV chapter of the dictionary named "Kelurnoma" (XVIII century) compiled by Muhammad Yaqub Chingi.

It is natural to create new types of vocabulary in order to meet the growing demands of the people. In current linguistics, work is being done on the issue of creating a thesaurus dictionary (Greek thesaios - source) or an ideographic dictionary. Thesaurus dictionary covers all the words whose meanings are connected with a certain word.

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